

Project Title **Implementing FAIR Workflows: a proof of concept study in the field of consciousness**

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D4.1 Dissemination Plan

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Authors **Xiaoli Chen** <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0207-2705>
Helena Cousijn <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6660-6214>
Kelly Stathis <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6133-4045>
Gabriela Mejias <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1598-7181>

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Executive summary

The Implementing FAIR Workflows Project aims to leverage existing persistent identifier infrastructure, research tools, and platforms to build a proof of concept research workflow for neuroscience research that is FAIR on inception. The project will provide an exemplar workflow to enable and encourage the wider neuroscience community to adopt FAIR practices.

The main dissemination goal is to build a community of first adopters, and provide a set of resources to equip future adopters with know-how of FAIR workflows so that they can start building realistic action plans. Efforts to achieve this goal include identifying and engaging different stakeholder groups to shape the project's adoption roadmap, validating the workflow implementation proposals, and producing resources and collaborating with partners external to the project to foster further adoption. This deliverable describes in detail the dissemination strategy, components, timeline, and success metrics to be used to achieve the goals of the project.

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Introduction

The Implementing FAIR Workflows project is a 3-year project, led by a core team of two organizations, involving five partners and two supporting organizations. The main goal of the project is to fully leverage the existing persistent identifier infrastructure, research tools and platforms, and develop a proof of concept research workflow for neuroscience research that's FAIR by inception, and provide an exemplar workflow to enable and encourage the wider neuroscience community to adopt FAIR practices.

In the project, scholarly infrastructure providers work side-by-side with a team of neuroscience researchers to identify challenges and opportunities in terms of research practices, and address these by developing a set of guiding principles for researchers. The project also builds a number of new integrations across research systems and platforms that enhance the FAIRness of research, and produce technical documentation and guidance throughout the project. It is crucial that relevant communities are informed, as well as actively involved in this process.

This document outlines the general strategy for the dissemination efforts the project is committed to, and the specific plans for achieving the strategic goals. The strategic goals for project output dissemination are threefold: broad exposure, continued relevance, and adoption and recognition in the community. We will achieve this by:

- Dissemination of information and resources during the project to involve the community in shaping the outputs:
 - Organize community-facing working meetings
 - Create synergy with other FAIR projects
 - Collaborate with first adopters
- Dissemination of information and resources post-project:
 - Maintain the resources by incorporating these into the organizational strategy
 - Align recommendations with community roadmaps
 - Continue to engage and attract adoption

This document is to be viewed and used in conjunction with the project communication plan¹, which focuses on the awareness raising aspect of dissemination and relevant communication channels.

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6302912>

Dissemination strategy

The dissemination efforts will be arranged to provide researchers and service integrators with a roadmap to navigate the FAIR landscape and concrete examples of how to put FAIR workflows into practice. In practical terms, this means identifying concrete stakeholder groups; producing a tailored implementation kit to inform stakeholder groups; and providing guiding principles combined with examples and channels of support to ensure successful adoption in the near and longer term. We identify two key areas for dissemination:

VALIDATION OF WORKFLOWS

Engage relevant stakeholders to disseminate in-progress workflows, iterate on use cases and adjust the adoption plan based on community feedback. As part of this we will:

- Identify specific stakeholder groups
- Share project work and approaches to invite feedback
- Identify opportunities of synergy with other FAIR projects

FOSTERING ADOPTION

Dissemination of outputs and adoption roadmaps for different workflows specified and validated in the above process, and ensuring the sustainability of resources that support adoption.

- Organize workshops and trainings for researchers
- Work with funders to implement FAIR research guidelines
- Integrate FAIR workflows resources into data management trainings
- Incorporate persistent identifier and metadata workflows on service platforms
- Hosting and maintenance of resources, integration documentation, and dashboard

Validation of Workflows

In the project, we will be engaging with stakeholders within and outside of the disciplinary community, to seek feedback on our approach to the development of the FAIR Workflows. Identifying the main stakeholder groups and inviting their input is crucial for 1) ensuring the project goals are kept aligned with developments and new initiatives in the FAIR community; and 2) validating that the use cases of the project outputs meet the needs of future adopters. We have identified a number of partners in these efforts, and are open to collaborate with other interested parties as the project gains more visibility in the wider community.

Key stakeholder groups

The validation efforts will be focused on engaging two groups of key stakeholders: 1) the researcher community, and 2) potential integrators (platforms) of FAIR supporting mechanisms.

Researchers and research institutions

The defining characteristic of the project is the focus on working directly with researchers to formulate a workflow that is easy to understand and adopt by the neuroscience research community. We intend to target researchers at different career stages, research institutions, and funders with distinct dissemination mechanisms.

Target group	Dissemination goal
Early career researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide guides and support for researchers to carry out Open Science practices
Principal Investigators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide value proposition and incentives to get PIs on board ● Provide an adoption plan for PIs to easily implement FAIR Workflows in their labs
Disciplinary community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide examples of adoption cases to demonstrate value ● Generate support structures in the community to sustain engagement
Institutes and universities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide resources to be integrated within existing training programs
Funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide guidelines for researchers to engage in FAIR practices

Table 1. Target groups identified in the researcher community and respective dissemination goals

Service integrators

Integrators are the research supporting organizations that are in a position to integrate services or functionalities into their existing workflows to support and enhance the FAIRness of research outputs. In the integrator category, we identified tools and platforms that do not yet have integrated PID workflows, and those that already have PID integrations in place. For the former group we will focus on supporting the initiation of a PID workflow, and for the latter enhancing existing workflows to increase metadata completeness and connectedness.

Target group	Dissemination goal
Tools and platform without PID integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide value proposition to PID integration ● Align metadata strategies to improve metadata completeness
Tools and platform with PID integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide integration best practice guide for benchmarking current integration ● Align metadata strategies to improve metadata completeness ● Provide recommendations for controlled vocabulary usage.

Table 2. Target groups identified in the integrator community and respective dissemination goals

Neuroscience and Informatics community

The International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility (INCF)

The mission of the International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility (INCF)² is to develop, evaluate, and endorse standards and best practices that embrace the principles of Open, FAIR, and Citable neuroscience.

The Director of Development and Communications of the INCF is part of the Project Advisory Committee to help us identify synergies with the INCF community. The INCF provides a platform for its annual plenary conference, its various working groups that have overlapping interests with the project, and a training hub that hosts resources endorsed by the community. We are planning to take advantage of all of these opportunities, starting with a FAIR Workflows session during the INCF Plenary in September 2022.

² <https://www.incf.org/>

OpenNeuro

OpenNeuro³ is a free and open platform for analyzing and sharing neuroimaging data. It is based around the Brain Imaging Data Structure specification.

We have established contact with OpenNeuro, and invited the project lead to sit on the Advisory Committee, to keep mutually informed about the scope of the content and metadata strategy. The former feeds into the research workflow design, and the latter into the domain specific metadata use cases. OpenNeuro is also an excellent case study of a data repository integrating customizable metadata templates, an integration also featured in the FAIR Workflows Project. OpenNeuro registers DataCite DOIs.

Brainlife

Brainlife⁴ is a free and secure reproducible neuroscience analysis platform.

As a researcher driven Open Science project, Brainlife represents the type of service and platform provider the Implementing FAIR Workflows project would engage with to advocate for the adoption of the FAIR integrator workflow. The director of Brainlife sits on the Advisory Committee of the project to provide an insider perspective and input for the development of project outputs, i.e. the dashboard and integrator adoption roadmap.

Open Science and FAIR communities

FAIR projects

Aside from leading the Implementing FAIR Workflows project, DataCite is also involved in a number of project efforts that are dedicated to the implementation of the FAIR principles at different levels. We plan to identify synergies among the ongoing projects to keep the goals aligned, and amplify impact of the outputs across projects.

The **FAIRCORE4EOSC⁵** project focuses on the development and realization of core components for the European Open Science Cloud. The mutual interests between the projects include interlinking research entities based on PIDs, enhancing the PID Graph, and metadata interoperability.

³ <https://openneuro.org>

⁴ <https://brainlife.io/about/>

⁵ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

The **FAIR-IMPACT**⁶ project will identify practices, policies, tools and technical specifications towards a FAIR data management cycle starting with real-life use cases in four different domains. The mutual interests between the projects are PID coordination, metadata, FAIR metrics and community engagement.

The **FAIR Island**⁷ project examines the impact of implementing optimal research data management policies and requirements, affording us the unique opportunity to look at the outcomes of strong data policies at a working field station. The mutual interests between the projects mainly focus on the project dashboard.

Research Data Alliance (RDA)

RDA⁸ provides a neutral space where its members can come together to develop and adopt infrastructure that promotes data-sharing and data-driven research. DataCite has been active in the RDA community, contributing and benefiting from the various interest groups and working groups that facilitate discussions and community engagement. In the project, we have jointly formed a Birds of a Feather group⁹ to generate interest in the interoperability between research platforms based on PID infrastructure. We conducted a session during the 2022 RDA plenary meeting, and we plan to continue cultivating the group and building resources to disseminate across the RDA community through collaboration.

Researcher-led Open Science communities

Outside of the neuroscience domain, many researcher-led groups are actively engaged in supporting the adoption of Open and FAIR research practices. We plan to reach out to the following communities to seek feedback and potential opportunity for collaboration.

The Turing Way¹⁰ is an open source, open collaboration, and community-driven project which maintains The Turing Way handbook to reproducible, ethical and collaborative data science.

The International Network of Open Science Communities (INOSC)¹¹ is a growing collaborative international network that fosters local organizations of researchers to engage in and share their experience of open science practices. The INOSC currently has more than a dozen active member communities.

⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

⁷ <https://fairisland.org/>

⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/building-enhanced-fair-workflows-through-use-pids-within-and-between-interoperable-research-tools>

¹⁰ <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/welcome.html>

¹¹ <https://www.startyourosc.com/docs/>

Fostering Adoption

Equipped with workflow specifications, documentation, and guides that are validated by the various stakeholders, we will engage in further adoption activities. This will involve continued public engagement with the community, publishing research articles based on project experience, as well as directly reaching out and partnering with organizations that are interested in advocating and implementing FAIR workflows in their community, to raise awareness and put in place appropriate integrations, bringing change to their current workflows.

Funders - Workflow specification

Funders can not only contribute to the FAIRness of research by implementing PIDs in the grant management process, but also improve FAIR compliant research practices by incorporating data management recommendations into grant agreements. In this project, we plan to work with a funder with a strong interest in Open Science to provide guidance for funders to take advantage of the global PID infrastructure, and recommendations on policy-making to improve the FAIRness of their funded projects.

Research organizations - Workshops and collaborative training

Many research organizations and academic libraries train researchers on open science practices such as pre-registration, data management, and data sharing. We plan to engage with research data librarians to co-organize workshops targeting the researchers. By extension, some local Communities of Practice organize train-the-trainers workshops to amplify impact. We were also approached by Arcadia Science¹² who seek to adopt FAIR practice recommendations in their workflow.

Service providers and digital research platforms - Technical documentation and papers

To respond to FAIR research policies and emerging practices, tools and platform providers can take advantage of the FAIR workflows specification and invest in functionalities that support output identification, richer metadata creation, and better interoperability between systems. In addition to working with the project partner organizations to implement a series of PID integrations and communicate and advocate for the efforts, we will also engage with potential first adopters external to the project to further validate use cases.

¹² <https://www.arcadia.science/>

Engaging researchers – Researcher guide

Engaging researchers to adopt FAIR practices has been a difficult needle to move in the transition to Open Science and FAIR research. In this project, we have the valuable opportunity to accompany a research team through the whole research process and document their experiences putting FAIR recommendations into practice. We will closely document the experience by tracking the time spent on Open and FAIR activities, and provide an overview of the challenges that arise and how we address these in the project.

One barrier to adoption is that researchers have difficulties associating the Open Science language to their domain language, and are thus unable to effectively apply the FAIR principles in their daily practices. In light of this, we aim to tell a clear story about FAIR research by mapping the Open Science lingo into practical terms, and building a core excellence group to provide examples and expertise.

Timeline

With the dissemination plan developed and finalized by the last quarter of the first project year, the stakeholder engagement efforts will continue throughout the rest of the project. In parallel, the community validation of the various use cases and workflow proposals will start by year two, aligned with the completion of the dashboard specification (D3.1) and metadata template (D2.2) milestones. We plan to start focusing on facilitating first adoption cases from the third quarter of the second year, and use the last project year to develop and finalize the adoption roadmap based on the integration and adoption experience of the project partners and first adopters. The relevant outputs and dissemination timeline can be found in Table 3.

DETAILS		Year 2				Year 3				PROJECT END
PROJECT QUARTER		Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	
Validation of Outputs	- Share domain-specific metadata templates with disciplinary community for validation and endorsement	█	█							
	- Validate use cases and usability of project level dashboard			█	█					
	- Deliver a guide to FAIR practices for researchers						█	█	█	
	- Align outputs with the deliverables of other FAIR projects	█	█	█	█	█				
Fostering Adoption	- Organize workshops and trainings for researchers									
	- Partner with two research organizations to integrate workflows into their training programs			█	█	█	█	█	█	
	- Partner with two system integrators to explore technical integration routes			█	█	█	█	█	█	
	- Work with a funder to implement recommendations in researcher materials									
	- Publish 2 preprints and at least 1 formal publication demonstrating the time resource commitment for FAIR practices									
	- Reach potential adopters through social media and monthly blog posts									

Table 3. Timeline for dissemination work¹³

¹³ Project timeline

Metrics

We plan to adopt both qualitative and quantitative methods to track the impact of dissemination efforts described in this document.

Goal	Method of Measure
Generate continued engagement (partially overlapping with the Communication Plan ¹⁴)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Virtual event attendance analysis (Zoom report) ● Evaluation survey analysis (Google form, Zoom poll, Menti questionnaire) ● Engagement generated through social media
Gain community endorsement for the project outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Public acknowledgement of the project outputs ● Support and testimony of use cases ● Track further discussions and commentaries generated in the community
Successful adoption cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Track number of integrations ● Track inclusion and acknowledgement in community recommendations

Table 4. Success metrics for dissemination

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6302912>